

RCP 8.5 Climate Change Versus Cost Effect on Optimal Scenario Mixes of Variable and Dispatchable Technologies in Morocco: Climate Model Inter-Comparison

Ayat-Allah Bouramdane¹

¹ Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique (LMD), École Polytechnique, Institut Polytechnique de Paris (IP Paris)

Abstract

Motivation

Climate change mitigation plans call for an increase in the use of Renewable Energy (RE) technologies. However, the later are in turn dependent on climate, which could affect the reliability and feasibility of future low-carbon supply systems.

Research Questions

This chapter particularly addresses the impacts that projected climate change will have on the Moroccan mix by the end-21st century (2071-2100) relative to the historical period (1976 - 2005) compared to cost effect by analyzing the interaction between solar technologies—Photovoltaic (PV) and Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) without and with Thermal Energy Storage (TES) of 6 hours (Solar Multiple of 2 or SM2)—with wind, taking into account the strength of both technologies in terms of sensitivity to temperature and solar irradiance taken from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5 (CMIP5).

Objectives and Methodology

To do, we take as objective not only to minimize the variance, but also to maximize the RE penetration at a given cost. Climate data obtained by COordinated Regional climate Downscaling EXperiment (CORDEX) in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region "MENA-CORDEX" are used. We perform two Regional Climate Model (RCM) simulations—the version 4 of the Rossby Centre regional Atmospheric model (RCA4) and the version 351 of the Weather Research and Forecasting model (WRF351)—over the study region using boundary conditions from four different Global Climate Models (GCMs)—Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques-Coupled Model (CNRM-CM5), Earth System Model (EC-EARTH), Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory's Earth System Model (GFDL-ESM2M), Community Climate System Model (CCSM4)—assuming one emission scenario, Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) 8.5, referred as a very high baseline emission scenario in the absence of policies to combat climate change. The impact of the latter on the mean wind and solar resources and Capacity Factors (CFs) along on the seasonal variability of CFs and demand are assessed, the sensitivity of optimal mixes (technological and geographical distribution of RE capacities) to climate change is analyzed under several scenarios of RE penetration, and the level of consistency in the climate projections and the main sources of uncertainty are examined; keeping the existing capacities and rental costs data.

General Findings

We find that RCP 8.5 climate change is relatively responsible for the variation of optimal mixes at high penetrations, but less so at low penetrations where this unlikely high-risk warming future induces a small changes in the mean and variance of CFs. Overall, the rental cost, storage and spatio-temporal complementarity govern the optimal capacity pathways while RCP 8.5 climate change is only responsible for the technology fraction signal. At maximum penetration, the capacity pathways are more sensitive to rental cost effect than to climate change-related risks, and thus all climate models agree on the technology fraction evolution between the historical and future simulations although non-robust at some specific penetration points due to changes in the mean CFs, but involves non-significant differences. Wind is (resp. PV and CSP are) resilient (resp. sensitive) to RCP 8.5 climate change. At low and high penetrations, the RCM uncertainty prevails more than GCM uncertainty. If high penetrations are targeted, this RCM uncertainty increases more for PV and wind

fraction—due to uncertainty in projected global tilted irradiance and wind speed changes—compared to CSP fraction—as all CMIP5 models tends to agree in the projection of temperature increase. At such high penetration scenarios, wind and CSP are (resp. PV is) sensitive (resp. resilient) to RCP 8.5 climate change. If low penetrations are targeted, optimal mixes are not impacted by cost and the RCM uncertainty increases for all technologies. RCA4 simulations driven by different GCMs (CNRM-CM5, EC-EARTH, GFDL-ESM2M) are largely consistent in the projected changes in optimal mixes expecting a moderate increase in wind and CSP share, and a decrease in PV share. However, these projections are still fairly inconsistent with WRF351 regional model forced by another GCM (CCSM4), expecting an increase in PV and a decline in wind and CSP shares. We also show that the surface temperature, solar irradiance and wind speed impact the solar and wind mean CFs and the regional patterns, but that is the seasonal correlation of CFs with the summer peak demand that governs the technological distribution in the mix. Overall, there is a low confidence in projected changes of resources between CMIP5 models, used in this study, which limit the ability to draw conclusions about what will happen in future optimal mixes with low proportions of REs since results are not only associated with model uncertainty but also uncertainty related to forcing conditions and to the natural internal variability of the climate system. We discuss, however, the conditions for climate-resilient RE mixes. We also show that the clearness index and wind speed parametrization— included in the CF models to take into account the intra-daily fluctuations of PV, CSP and wind CFs not resolved by daily CORDEX climate data, keeping a daily record of the temperature—may also be responsible for the largest uncertainties in the mean-variance results, whatever the penetration scenario, compared to hourly simulations from the Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications 2 (MERRA-2) climate reanalysis. The fraction of CSP with small amount of thermal storage decreases whatever the model and the penetration scenario and thus large storage (more than 17 hours per day on average or $SM > 4$) is needed if CSP-TES is considered in future optimal mixes. At high penetrations, the geographical distribution of PV and CSP/CSP-TES is sensitive to changes in climate with high climate-sensitivity models while that of wind is only sensitive to climate data sources at maximum-penetration mix. At low penetrations, the geographical distribution of wind and solar technologies are neither altered by climate change nor by climate data sources.

Keywords— Optimal Scenario Mixes, Variable/Dispatchable Technologies, Climate Change, Morocco.

Published: This study has been published as a chapter [Bouramdane et al. (2021), Chapter 5], on October 20, 2021.

References

- [Bouramdane et al. (2021)] Bouramdane, A.A. Scenarios of Large-Scale Solar Integration with Wind in Morocco: Impact of Storage, Cost, Spatio-Temporal Complementarity and Climate Change. Ph.D. Thesis, Institut Polytechnique de Paris, Palaiseau, France, 2021.